

A STUDY ON FACTORS THAT AFFECTS CONSUMER PREFERENCES IN PURCHASING SKIN CARE PRODUCT

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Abstract:

The most important step in caring for your skin comes in understanding your specific skin type and how it adapts to certain circumstances or seasonality. Your skin is your body's largest organ, as complex and intelligent as your heart, lungs, liver and other vital organs. Using cleansers and treatments that are too harsh, even if they are recommended for excessive oiliness, may send the signal to your skin that more oil is actually needed. Conversely, applying moisturizers that are too thick or heavy can result in decreased natural oil production, resulting in even drier skin. Taking the time to learn your skin's specific needs will help you to choose the right options that will balance skin resulting in a healthier, more radiant complexion. Every person's skin is unique, but there are a few common skin types that may help you to identify where your skin fits in the most. The three main skin types are commonly referred to as Oily, Normal/Combination and Dry. People are more conscious about their product brand as many of them use and even recommend using herbal products. Customers with normal skin tend to use more skin care products and they fall under the age group of 21 to 25 and moisturizer is found to be most popular among all age group. Attractive displays about the product grab more customer's attention while purchasing the skin care product. Thus, the purchase behavior of the customers tend to fall on the goodwill of the company and the recommendation given by their friends, the parlor they visit and the attractive promotions given by the company.

Key Words: Consumer Preference, Attractive Displays & Skin Care Product

Introduction:

Manufacturers and marketers need to gain a deeper understanding of consumer and shopper behaviour (going beyond traditional consumer/market research), and then work out the appropriate value proposition and delivery channels for their basket of goods and services. It is well known fact that the success of any business organization stems from company's ability to understand and influence consumer behaviour. This study is needed to consider when designing and implementing marketing programs. Failure to understand the dynamic buyer behaviour and improper allocation and coordination of resources will lead the organization to great losses. The better marketers are at understanding consumer behaviour, the more successful they will be at influencing consumers purchase behaviour. There are three sections of consumer behaviour that need to be addressed carefully: psychological influences, socio-cultural influences and situational influences. The marketers have to go through a number of challenges in selling products like Skin care products as they have to be applied directly on human skins, body and other parts. There is a perceived risk of dissatisfaction in the consumers as far as its benefits are concerned. It is necessary to study the consumer buying decision process in this regard.

The core concept of marketing revolves around the decisions consumers and organizations take in buying certain products May it be goods, services or ideas. While buying certain products, consumers become highly sensitive of their quality, expected benefits and the way of using it. Courtland L Bovee" and John V Thill (1992) define consumer behaviour as consumer's all the actions involved in selecting, purchasing, using and disposing of goods and services. Consumers buying behaviour is a complex phenomenon with a number of factors that affect their behaviour when they involve themselves with buying process.

Improved technology, better education, advancement in science and economic growth has provided people with a chance to better standard of living. With increased purchasing power and increasing number of dual earning has made people more conscious towards beauty, hygiene and better life style. Today women are more active, liberal moving ahead and taking part in every walk of life so they became more concerned towards their looks and appearance. It effects the rapid growth of beauty care industry. Skin care products not only increases the physical appearance of person but also the confidence and assurance of individual to meet the challenges of society with great ease than ever before. To meet this growing demand of skin care products by women not only domestic companies but many multinational companies enter the market place to meet the growing demand of beauty care products. There are many factors which affect the choice of brands, make and type of products to be purchased. Some women buy skin care products because of brand, some buy skin care product because of price, some buy skin care product because of friends'and relative's recommendations and

others buy skin care product because of packaging design. Hence marketers need to consider many factors concerning women decision to buy skin care products.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To analyze present market for skin care product.
- ✓ To identify effectiveness of the promotional activities for skin care products.
- ✓ To have a consumer opinion about the skin care product.
- ✓ To identify the promotional strategy for different level of consumer.

Scope of the Study: The scope of the study is basically limited to the analysis of the present market for skincare product and consumer preference for purchasing skin care products. Scope in this section is very broad to analyze, as information is quite available. Human resource department is the major scope while doing this study and also the website has helped me a lot to collect data.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ Information about the current market growth was hard to get.
- ✓ Due to lack of time for the study period the researcher could not able to get more samples.

Research Methodology:

A research design in the overall plan or program of research. A research design or model indicates a plan of action to be carried out in connection with a proposed research work.

Period of the Study:

The study was conducted for a period of 3 months.

Area of Study:

The area of the study is limited to Coimbatore city. It is popularly known as Manchester of South India, is situated in the western part of the state Tamil Nadu.

Sample Size:

Sample size is 170 responses.

Statistical Tools Used:

Percentage analysis and Chi-square test

Analysis and Interpretation:

Gender & Skin Type:

			Skin Type				Total
			Dry	Normal	Oily	Sensitive	
Gender	Male	Count	12	33	30	0	75
		Total %	7.10%	19.40%	17.60%	0.00%	44.10%
	Female	Count	22	34	26	13	95
		Total %	12.90%	20.00%	15.30%	7.60%	55.90%
Total		Count	34	67	56	13	170
		Total %	20.00%	39.40%	32.90%	7.60%	100%

Interpretation:

From the above table it shows that, 55.9% are female and 44.1% are male out of which 39.4% respondents have normal skin, 32.9% respondents have oily skin, 20.0% respondents have dry skin and 7.6% respondents have sensitive skin.

Age & Skin Type:

			Skin Type				Total	
			Dry	Normal	Oily	Sensitive		
Age	18-20	Count	3	8	9	4	24	
		Total %	1.80%	4.70%	5.30%	2.40%	14.10%	
	21-25	Count	24	43	35	6	108	
		Total %	14.10%	25.30%	20.60%	3.50%	63.50%	
	26-30	Count	4	9	7	2	22	
		Total %	2.40%	5.30%	4.10%	1.20%	12.90%	
	31-40	Count	3	5	3	1	12	
		Total %	1.80%	2.90%	1.80%	0.60%	7.10%	
	40 and Above	Count	0	2	2	0	4	
		Total %	0.00%	1.20%	1.20%	0.00%	2.40%	
	Total		Count	34	67	56	13	170
			Total %	20.00%	39.40%	32.90%	7.60%	100%

Interpretation:

From the above table it shows that, 63.5% are 21-25 age group, 14.1% are 18-20 age group, 12.9% are 26-30 age group, 7.1% are 31-40 age group and 2.4% are 40 above age group out of which 39.4% respondents have normal skin, 32.9% respondents have oily skin, 20.0% respondents have dry skin and 7.6%

respondents have sensitive skin.

Gender & IMP Factor While Purchasing SCP:

			IMP Factor While Purchasing SCP						
			Remove Acne or Pimple	Fairness	Sunburn Protection	Moisturizer	Oil Control	Water Resistant	Total
Gender	Male	Count	23	8	12	14	17	1	75
		Total %	13.50%	4.70%	7.10%	8.20%	10.00%	0.60%	44.10%
	Female	Count	14	23	21	25	10	2	95
		Total %	8.20%	13.50%	12.40%	14.70%	5.90%	1.20%	55.90%
Total		Count	37	31	33	39	27	3	170
		Total %	21.80%	18.20%	19.40%	22.90%	15.90%	1.80%	100%

Interpretation:

From the above table it shows that, 55.9% are female and 44.1% are male out of which 22.9% purchases moisturizer products, 21.8% purchases remove acne or pimple products, 19.4% purchases sunburn protection products, 18.2% purchases fairness products, 15.9% purchases oil control products and 1.8% purchases water resistant products.

Occupation & Magazine/Newspaper:

			MAG/NEWS		Total
			Yes	No	
Occupation	Employee	Count	6	66	72
		Total %	3.5%	38.8%	42.4%
	Student	Count	6	92	98
		Total %	3.5%	54.1%	57.6%
Total		Count	12	158	170
		Total %	7.1%	92.9%	100%

Interpretation:

From the above table it shows that, 57.6% are students and 42.4% are employees out of which 92.9% respondents will not purchase according to magazines/newspaper and 7.1% respondents purchase according to magazines/newspaper.

			Monthly Expenses					Total	
			Less than 500	500-1000	1000-2000	2000-3000	3000 above		
Salary	8000-10000	Count	11	4	0	0	0	15	
		Total %	6.50%	2.40%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	8.80%	
	10000-20000	Count	7	9	3	0	0	19	
		Total %	4.10%	5.30%	1.80%	0.00%	0.00%	11.20%	
	20000-30000	Count	8	3	3	0	0	14	
		Total %	4.70%	1.80%	1.80%	0.00%	0.00%	8.20%	
	30000-40000	Count	5	5	0	1	0	11	
		Total %	2.90%	2.90%	0.00%	0.60%	0.00%	6.50%	
	40000 & Above	Count	9	6	1	1	0	17	
		Total %	5.30%	3.50%	0.60%	0.60%	0.00%	10.00%	
	Not Earning	Count	68	23	2	0	1	94	
		Total %	40.00%	13.50%	1.20%	0.00%	0.60%	55.30%	
	Total		Count	108	50	9	2	1	170
			Total %	63.50%	29.40%	5.30%	1.20%	0.60%	100%

Interpretation:

From the above table it shows that, 55.3% respondents are not earning, 11.2% respondents have 10000-20000 salary, 10.0% respondents have 40000 above salary, 8.8% respondents have 8000-10000 salary, 8.2% respondents have 20000-30000 salary and 6.5% have 30000-40000 salary out of which 63.5% respondents monthly expenses is less than 500, 29.4% respondents monthly expenses is between 500-1000, 5.3% respondents monthly expenses is between 1000-2000, 1.2% respondents monthly expenses is between 2000-3000 and 0.6% respondents monthly expenses is 3000 above.

Salary and Buying Place of SCP:

			Buying Place of SCP						Total
			General Store	Cosmetics Store	Online	Super Market	Drug/Pharmacy	Shopping Mall	
8000-	Count	5	2	0	2	3	3	15	

	10000	Total %	2.90%	1.20%	0.00%	1.20%	1.80%	1.80%	8.80%
	10000-20000	Count	1	6	4	4	1	3	19
		Total %	0.60%	3.50%	2.40%	2.40%	0.60%	1.80%	11.20%
	20000-30000	Count	3	3	0	4	3	1	14
		Total %	1.80%	1.80%	0.00%	2.40%	1.80%	0.60%	8.20%
	30000-40000	Count	1	1	0	3	1	5	11
		Total %	0.60%	0.60%	0.00%	1.80%	0.60%	2.90%	6.50%
	40000 & Above	Count	1	3	1	4	2	6	17
		Total %	0.60%	1.80%	0.60%	2.40%	1.20%	3.50%	10.00%
	Not Earning	Count	19	21	9	13	18	14	94
		Total %	11.20%	12.40%	5.30%	7.60%	10.60%	8.20%	55.30%
Total	Count		30	36	14	30	28	32	170
	Total %		17.60%	21.20%	8.20%	17.60%	16.50%	18.80%	100%

Interpretation:

From the above table it shows that, 55.3% respondents are not earning, 11.2% respondents have 10000-20000 salary, 10.0% respondents have 40000 above salary, 8.8% respondents have 8000- 10000 salary , 8.2% respondents have 20000-30000 salary and 6.5% have 30000-40000 salary out of which 21.2% respondents purchases from cosmetics store, 18.8% purchases from shopping mall, 17.6% purchases from super markets, 17.6% purchases from general store, 16.5% purchases from drug/pharmacy and 8.2% purchases from online.

Occupation & Television:

		TV		Total	
		Yes	No		
Occupation	Employee	Count	23	49	72
		Total %	13.50%	28.80%	42.40%
	Student	Count	29	69	98
		Total %	17.10%	40.60%	57.60%
Total		Count	52	118	170
		Total %	30.60%	69.40%	100%

Interpretation:

From the above table it shows that, 57.6% are students and 42.4% are employees out of which 69.4% respondents will not purchases according to television and 30.6% respondents will purchases according to television.

Occupation & Internet:

		Internet		Total	
		Yes	No		
Occupation	Employee	Count	29	43	72
		Total %	17.10%	25.30%	42.40%
	Student	Count	46	52	98
		Total %	27.10%	30.60%	57.60%
Total		Count	75	95	170
		Total %	44.10%	55.90%	100%

Interpretation:

From the above table it shows that, 57.6% are students and 42.4% are employees out of which, 55.9% respondents will purchases according to internet and 44.1% respondents purchases according to internet.

Monthly Expenses:

	Observed N	Expected N
Less than 500	108	34
500-1000	50	34
1000-2000	9	34
2000-3000	2	34
3000 above	1	34

Interpretation:

From the above chi-square test the significant value is 0.00 which below the table value 0.05 so null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant association between monthly expenses and promotional activates. Hence, it is inferred that the monthly expenses of the respondent is an influencing factor in the promotional activates that grab their attention.

Findings:

- ✓ The result shows that, 44.1% are male and 55.9% are female out of which 39.4% respondents have normal skin, 32.9% respondents have oily skin, 20.0% respondents have dry skin and 7.6% respondents have sensitive skin.
- ✓ The result shows that, 14.1% are 18-20 age group, 63.5% are 21-25 age group, 12.9% are 26-30 age group, 7.1% are 31-40 age group and 2.4% are 40 above age group out of which
- ✓ 39.4% respondents have normal skin, 32.9% respondents have oily skin, 20.0% respondents have dry skin and 7.6% respondents have sensitive skin.
- ✓ The result shows that, 44.1% are male and 55.9% are female out of which 22.9% purchases moisturizer products, 21.8% purchases remove acne or pimple products, 19.4% purchases sunburn protection products, 18.2% purchases fairness products, 15.9% purchases oil control products and 1.8% purchases water resistant products.
- ✓ The result shows that, 14.1% are 18-20 age group, 63.5% are 21-25 age group, 12.9% are 26-30 age group, 7.1% are 31-40 age group and 2.4% are 40 above age group out of which 22.9% purchases moisturizer products, 21.8% purchases remove acne or pimple products, 19.4% purchases sunburn protection products, 18.2% purchases fairness products, 15.9% purchases oil control products and 1.8% purchases water resistant products.
- ✓ The result shows that, 42.4% are employees and 57.6% are students out of which 60.0% respondents will not use samples and 40.0% respondents uses samples.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Customer survey should be taken before launching a new product in the market.
- ✓ Equal importance should be given for both female and male as skin care products is not only used by the females.
- ✓ The company should create more awareness on Newspaper, Poster, Beauty saloon.
- ✓ More concentration should be given to 21-25 age group as they are the one who uses the skin care products more.
- ✓ Attractive packaging can be made to attract the customer.
- ✓ Brand equity through advertisement the companies can increase their brand name and sales.
- ✓ Increase promotional activities through poster, gift items, discounts.
- ✓ Product quality is a main factor for customer satisfaction so make more importance in the quality of skin care products.
- ✓ The product price should be affordable for the customer as they are willing to buy less than 500 range products.
- ✓ More products which is suitable for the normal skin should be introduced to the market.
- ✓ Now a days the customer will focus on herbal products so try to avoid chemicals in skin care products.

Conclusion:

The perception towards the purchase of skin care products changes among people as there are lots of marketing strategies used by the companies to attract people toward them. The focuses on the buying behavior of people towards the skin care products and to gain knowledge on the products available in the market. These days both male and female uses skin care product as they tend to grow more beauty conscious. Customer's purchases their skin care product on the basis of promotional activities and their monthly expenses is also an important factor while purchasing a skin care product. People are more conscious about their product brand as many of them use and even recommend to use herbal products. Customers with normal skin tend to use more skin care products and they fall under the age group of 21 to 25 and moisturizer is found to be most popular among all age group. Attractive displays about the product grab more customers attention while purchasing the skin care product. Thus, the purchase behavior of the customers tend to fall on the goodwill of the company and the recommendation given by their friends, the parlor they visit and the attractive promotions given by the company.

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